

***Rmg8* confers resistance to the Bangladeshi lineage of the wheat blast fungus**

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First reported in South America, wheat blast, caused by the fungus *Magnaporthe oryzae* (Syn. *Pyricularia oryzae*), has recently spread to Bangladesh and is threatening neighboring South Asian countries. To date, only a few resistance genes have been identified to function against wheat blast. Whether these genes are effective against the Bangladeshi lineage of the wheat blast fungus is unknown. Here, we found that a hexaploid common wheat line S-615 carrying the gene *Rmg8* is resistant to *M. oryzae* Bangladeshi isolate BTJP4-1 but susceptible to Brazilian isolate N06047. These findings are consistent with the observation that *AvrRmg8*, which encodes the avirulence effector protein recognized by *Rmg8*, is present in Bangladeshi isolates of the wheat blast fungus. These results indicate that *Rmg8* could contribute to breeding blast resistant wheat varieties adapted to South Asian conditions.

Wheat blast is a destructive fungal disease of wheat caused by *Magnaporthe oryzae* (Syn. *Pyricularia oryzae*) (Urashima et al., 1993). The disease was first discovered in Paraná State of Brazil in 1985, and spread rapidly to other South American countries, such as Bolivia, Paraguay, and Argentina, where it infects up to 3 million hectares and causes serious crop losses (Kholi et al., 2011). It was feared that wheat blast could expand beyond South America and threaten food security in wheat growing areas such as Asia (Kholi et al., 2011). Indeed, in February 2016, wheat blast was spotted in Bangladesh—its first report in Asia. Genetic analyses revealed that the pathogen most likely originated from South America (Islam et al., 2016). Wheat is the second major food source in Bangladesh, after rice. The blast disease has caused up to 90% yield losses in more than 15,000 hectares in the 2016 season, and continues to threaten wheat production in Bangladesh. Scientists fear that the pathogen could spread further to other wheat growing areas in South Asia (Islam et al., 2019).

To date only a handful of resistance genes have been identified to be effective against the wheat blast fungus. These include *Rmg2* and *Rmg3* (Zhan et al., 2008), *Rmg7* (Tagle et al., 2015), and *Rmg8* (Anh et al., 2015). However, whether these *Rmg* genes are effective against the wheat blast isolates from Bangladesh remains unknown. Also, some of these *Rmg* genes may not be very useful under South Asian conditions. *Rmg2* and *Rmg3* are not effective at the heading stage and may not be useful for field deployment because the wheat blast fungus strikes wheat spikes in the field (Anh et al., 2018). *Rmg7* is reported not to be effective at temperatures above 26 °C (Anh et al., 2018), and therefore may not be useful in the wheat fields of Bangladesh. Thus, *Rmg8* is the leading candidate resistance gene that could be useful in Bangladesh. Furthermore, the effector gene *AvrRmg8*, which is targeted by *Rmg8*, is present in wheat blast isolates from Bangladesh and is expressed in field lesions sampled from the Bangladesh wheat blast epidemic of 2016 (Wang et al., 2018).

Here, we investigated whether *Rmg8* is effective against a wheat blast isolate representative of the Bangladeshi clonal lineage. We report that hexaploid wheat S-615 carrying the gene *Rmg8* is resistant to an isolate of wheat blast fungus from Bangladesh under laboratory inoculation conditions.

Materials and methods

Conidiospores (1×10^5 spores ml⁻¹) from Bangladesh isolate BTJP4-1 and Brazilian isolate N06047 were resuspended in 0.25% gelatine and either spot- or spray-inoculated on detached leaves of two-week old wheat plants (“Vuka” and S-615). Detached leaves were placed in sealed Petri-dishes containing water agar in a growth cabinet set at 25 °C temperature with 18/6 hours light/dark cycles. Spot inoculation was performed by placing 5 µl droplets of conidial suspension on detached leaves, and wicking away droplets after 24 hours. Spray inoculation was performed using an artist’s paintbrush, and placing leaves in high humidity in the dark for 24 hours. Symptoms were scored 5 days post inoculation.

Results

Wheat line Vuka, which doesn’t carry *Rmg8*, was susceptible to both Bangladesh isolate BTJP4-1 and Brazilian isolate N06047 with infection symptoms observed in both spot- and spray-inoculations (Fig. 1 A, C, E, G). Line S-615, which carries *Rmg8*, was resistant to BTJP4-1 in both spot- and spray-inoculations (Fig. 1 B and F) showing localised hypersensitive response. However, S-615 was susceptible to N06047 in spray-inoculation experiments (Fig. 1 H), whereas it showed slightly smaller lesions in spot-inoculation experiments (Fig. 1 D) compared to those on Vuka (Fig. 1 C).

Fig. 1. Symptoms of wheat blast infection on detached leaves by fungal isolates from Bangladesh (BTJP4-1) and Brazil (N06047) on wheat lines Vuka (A, E, C, and G) and S-615 (B, D, F, and H) 5 days after inoculation.

Conclusions

Hexaploid wheat S-615 carrying *Rmg8* is resistant to infection by a Bangladesh isolate of the wheat blast fungus under laboratory conditions. This is consistent with the observation that *AvrRmg8*, which encodes the avirulence effector protein recognised by *Rmg8*, is expressed during wheat blast infection in Bangladesh (Wang et al., 2018). Additionally, preliminary analyses from our laboratories revealed that the wheat blast epidemics in Bangladesh during 2016 and 2017 are caused by a clonal lineage, and the isolate used in this report belongs to this lineage. Therefore, *Rmg8* is likely to be effective against wheat blast in Bangladesh. However, it should be noted that S-615 is susceptible to the Brazilian wheat blast isolate under the laboratory conditions we used, although its performance in the field has yet to be tested. Wang et al. (2018)

reported recently that *RmgGR119*, another resistance gene, confers a stronger resistance against the wheat blast fungus when combined with *Rmg8*. These results are encouraging news for breeding and deployment of resistant wheat varieties with *Rmg8* in Bangladesh and other South Asian countries.

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